

Project Deliverable D-JRP17- WP7.Del5

Workpackage 5

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: APHA, FLI, IZSAM,
INIAV, INSA, IZS, WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

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DELIVERABLE REPORT D-JRP17-WP7.DEL5: REPORT OF THE 2ND ANNUAL WORKSHOP INCLUDING EXCHANGES BETWEEN PARTNERS AND INPUTS FROM EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS

Description of the task

This work package is dedicated to the general coordination and management of the project including all administrative and financial issues. The annual workshop ensures the regular exchanges among partners, presents advances of the project. Partners join together to present the results of each work package, decide on public communications, changes in DMPs, and perform SWAT analysis, to identify risks and threats for the project. This will ensure the timely implementation of the tasks, the smooth running of the project and successful dissemination of outputs.

This year, still the safest and the most efficient was to organise the two day online workshop.

List of participating institutions: ANSES, APHA, BfR, FLI, INIAV, INSA, IZSAM, WBVR

Workshop was divided into two parts: presentation of each Work Package advancements; organisation of WP6 – final Toolkit compiling, contribution of each WP and surveillance system with information distribution.

WP1 – Recording the situation of brucellosis in emergent wild and environmental reservoirs

- First two tasks have been finished: a) Mapping of existing data on emerging *Brucella* spp.; b) Harmonization and sharing of sampling protocols and epidemiology survey; c) Analytical protocols for serology/bacteriology were prepared and added to the SharePoint platform; d) List of new biological collections (sera, tissues, environmental, strains).
- Still to be finished are: a) Characterization of serological responses and isolation data; b) Integrative analysis of the infection situation in the emerging reservoirs.
- So far over 1000 samples have been tested by five partner's laboratories, but there is still considerable number of samples to be registered in the Master data table. Out of these samples, 82 were positive in qPCR reactions either for *Brucella* spp or *Ochrobactrum* spp. and further analyses as well as strain isolation data should be completed until this summer.
- For this year main goal is synthesis and analysis of epidemiological as well as phenotypical data. In the same time integrative analysis approach will be developed.
- The main contributions of this WP to final toolkit will be identification of main reservoirs for emerging *Brucella* spp. ; definition of the best sampling strategy; decision tree for diagnosis and identification of outbreaks to reduce One Health impact.
- The time line for finishing deliverables two and three has been presented.
- At least one publication is in preparation for the end of the year as well as full participation in the annual Brucellosis conference in Italy.

WP2 – Recording the situation of emerging brucellosis in human

- The continued targeted sample collection and analysis is still ongoing in Portugal.
- The additional strategy includes testing of professionally exposed humans to *B. canis*. The collaboration with School of veterinary medicine and one veterinary clinic in Lisbon have been established in order to perform serology tests on exposed students and personnel.

- In addition to these activities, WP2 will produce the summary of human Brucellosis cases in Portugal in order to try identify critical points for human contamination and transmission routes.
- In collaboration with INIAV, all collected sera will be tested using *B. ovis* and *B. canis* (both rough species) antigens, to analyse their use in detection of human cases infected with *B. canis* since no test exists so far.

WP3 – Genomic characterisation of *Brucella* detected from samples and selected isolates

- First two deliverables have been finished at the beginning of 2022: a) Standard operating procedures for the extraction of *Brucella* DNA from complex matrices; b) Harmonised whole genome sequencing and bioinformatic protocols.
- The other two deliverables will be finished until August 2022: Molecular typing from emerging *Brucella* isolates; Rapid detection assay(s) for atypical strains using clade specific markers.
- The major problem for both deliverables is absence of isolated strains from WP1. Therefore consortium decided to use existing atypical *Brucella* strains from each partners' collections.
- The main contributions of this WP to final toolkit will be improved detection of *Brucella* spp. from complex matrices; harmonised Whole Genome Sequencing protocols and bioinformatics protocols allowing data sharing and comparisons; comprehensive pipeline for analysis of phylogenetic relationships of atypical *Brucella* strains to describe population structure and aid placement of newly described strains.
- Finally, it is planned to design and evaluate among partners the atypical *Brucella* molecular assays.
- Several scientific publications have been planned:
 - Microbiology Resource Announcement – Improved/completed reference genomes for type strains of atypical species (*B. inopinata* and *B. vulpis*).
 - Evaluation of soil DNA extraction methods
 - Comprehensive evaluation of phylogenetic relationships/population structure of atypical *Brucella* spp. can be published only at the end of the project, when all additional analyses have been performed: core genome SNPs; wgSNP, MLST, MLVA.

WP4 – Phenotypic characterisation of *Brucella* detected from samples and selected isolates

- First two deliverables of this work package will be finished on time in June and August 2022 (respectively). Since there have been several changes in personnel deliverable three has to be postponed for 5-6 months ae, the end of the project.
- Manufacturer has discontinued the micronaut plates. Therefore, attention turned towards testing the bacteriological differences between typical and atypical species in the conditions of starvation and various substrate utilisation.
- In the same time the electron microscopy has been employed as additional analysis tool.
- The main contributions of this WP to final toolkit will be harmonised protocols for the AMR characterisation; classification of motility characteristics and substrate use for identification of atypical *Brucella* spp.
- Scientific publications have been planned for the end of the project as well as communications on international Brucellosis conference.

WP5 – Zoonotic potential and virulence

- This work package started in the second half of last year. So far, tool selection have been defined; classification of zoonotic potential based on literature and consortium suggestions; assembly of macrophage cell lines from humans and animals for *in vitro* testing; SOPs for *in vitro* infection.
- The main contributions of this WP to final toolkit will be SOPs for in vitro zoonotic potential characterisation; characterise the expression of bacterial virulence genes in different zoonotic classes; identification of cytokine profiles that mark zoonotic potential.
- The time line of the WP has been presented without major delays from initial project plans.

WP6 – Round table

- Several major points have been discussed.
- The main goal is to develop a toolkit for detection and characterisation of emerging *Brucella* species and reservoirs. This operational toolbox will regroup: reference databases, harmonised protocols, guidance on interpretation, tracking systems, flowcharts on outbreak investigations including

emerging *Brucella* and reservoirs. This will mean validation of new characterisation approaches including functional markers: viability, virulence, resistance to antibiotics, and development of *in vitro* models.

- Data that will be integrated in the final toolkit:
 - i) the detection and investigation of these pathogens from different sources
 - under various epidemiological contexts in terms of natural landscape, livestock demographics and wildlife populations in Europe;
 - ii) the characterisation of emerging *Brucella* by identification of genomic and phenotypic variability via high throughput methods
 - (NGS, molecular tests, proteomics, metabolomics);
 - iii) the understanding of virulence and zoonotic potential through *in vivo* and *in vitro* infection models.
- Each WP discussed its contribution and it was decided to separate a toolkit in four parts: Laboratory methods and SOPs, Outbreak investigation utilities, Surveillance tools, and communication methods and dynamic databases (Appendix 1).
- It was proposed to share the final toolkit on EU Referent Laboratory for Brucellosis website. It will be publically available and will have integrative interactive form.
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External presentation:

- Sylvain Falala and Elena Arevska presented the PADlweb project. The project constructs fully automated information collection system based on Google News and RSS alerts system. Based on the key words the system uses supervised learning approach of artificial intelligence to sort available data and present the news as well as sort the data in databases, maps and information systems.
- The consortium recognised the usefulness of this approach and it was decided to explore the possibility to include it in a final toolkit.

Project SWOT Analysis (Appendix 2):

Partners accentuated as major project strengths:

- institutional supports,
- cooperation between work packages,
- increased exchange of new methodologies for Brucellosis detection among partners
- Creation of several networks,
- Potential to make use of existing collections among partners,
- Availability of management team,
- Creation of *in vitro* models for bacterial infections,
- Harmonisation of bioinformatics pipeline exchanges that do not require strain exchanges on a big scale

In the same partners pointed out major weaknesses, such as:

- Low number of human samples,
- Sharing strains/samples between partners is problematic, and MTA, shipping and legislations organisation takes very long time,
- Low likelihood of identifying further novel atypical *Brucella* spp.,
- Still improve commitment of partners and share of results,
- Samples assessment,
- Bioinformatics is important tool, but only when differences are on genomic level.

The opportunities this project and current global situation created are following:

- Comparison of methods among partners,
- Improvement of knowledge and surveillance methods of emerging *Brucella* spp., in wild reservoirs and environment,
- Establishment of small groups for further collaboration between different animal and public health sectors and between disciplines,
- Opportunities presented by emerging *B. canis* infections throughout Europe,
- Comparisons between human and animal strains that circulate in Europe,
- Increased awareness of Brucellosis risks,

- Agility and empowerment of research team,
- Cooperation in data evaluation,
- Identification of novel directions and ideas on virulence/ zoonotic potential

Major threats that can occur in the last year are:

- Still ongoing pandemic,
- Low budget to allow permanency of the study,
- Gaps and not complete data in available data bases,
- New tasks on *B. canis*,
- Emerging strains too different from known well characterised strains,
- Severely limited time to reach overall goals,
- No human isolates,

Annual plan for 2022:

	M49-50	M51-52	M53-54	M55-56	M57-58	M59-60
WP1						
T2						
T3						
WP2						
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WP7						
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T4						

APPENDIX 1:

APPENDIX 2:

